

1 **Hedgehog or Fox?**

2 **Theories of Change for Dryland Cereals in Eastern Africa**

3
4 Alastair Orr ¹

5 Elijah Muange ²

6
7 *'The fox knows many things, but the hedgehog knows one big thing'.*

8 Archilochus of Paros (ca.680-645 BCE), quoted Berlin (1988).

9 **Abstract**

10 *ICRISAT's research strategy for sorghum and millets is based on market-led development.*
11 *We analyse the construction of this Theory of Change and its application to Eastern Africa*
12 *using evidence from the HOPE project. We trace the evolution of market discourse in ICRISAT*
13 *and ask why this discourse became so influential. The scale of commercialisation was limited*
14 *and its effect on intensification was mixed. A Green Revolution for dryland cereals will come*
15 *from improved varieties that mature early and evade drought. A modified Theory of Change*
16 *for dryland cereals requires greater recognition of household food security, farmer agency,*
17 *and regional heterogeneity.*

18
19 **1. Introduction**

20 Theories of Change have become a prominent feature in the design of agricultural research
21 programmes. In 2011 the Consultative Group for International Research (CGIAR) – a
22 consortium of 15 international agricultural research centres (IARCs) – unveiled its first Strategy
23 and Results Framework (CGIAR, 2011). Research was structured into 15 CGIAR Research
24 Programmes (CRPs) which have begun to define their strategies using Theories of Change
25 (Apgar et. al., 2017; Douthewaite and Hoffecker, 2017; Mayne and Johnson, 2015). This is
26 part of a wider shift to 'results-based management' (Eyben, 2015). Alongside this rising tide of
27 managerialism, however, there is now a growing awareness of how the knowledge in such
28 Theories is constructed. The 'linguistic turn' of postmodernism has led to a greater sensitivity
29 to development 'discourse'. The language of development – its 'narratives' (Roe, 1991), its
30 use of 'buzzwords' (Cornwall, 2007; Cornwall and Brock, 2005) and how its problems are
31 'framed' (Gasper and Apthorpe, 1996) – has itself become the object of critical scrutiny. As
32 agricultural research makes growing use of Theories of Change, there is also a growing need
33 to unpack them in order to understand or, indeed, to resist the way they shape our thinking
34 about smallholder agriculture.

35 A Theory of Change is a generalisation about causation. Two Theories of Change have been
36 widely used to explain the intensification of agriculture in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). One is
37 that intensification is caused by population pressure on limited land (Boserup, 1965). The
38 second views intensification as the result of commercialisation, which makes it profitable for
39 farmers to increase production and the amount they can sell (Pingali et. al., 1987). These
40 competing Theories frame the continuing debate over intensification in SSA (Jayne et. al.,

¹ Corresponding Author. Honorary Research Fellow, ICRISAT-Nairobi, Kenya

² Lecturer, Machakos University, Kenya

41 2019). Although these Theories are rivals, they also have something in common: they are both
42 universal models that are applied in radically different contexts. Using the metaphor of the
43 hedgehog and the fox, they are not foxes, which can adapt to fit a variety of contexts, but
44 hedgehogs which know 'one big thing'.

45 One way of testing such generalisations is through case studies of research and development
46 projects. HOPE (Harnessing Opportunities for Productivity Enhancement), a project funded
47 by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF), embraced a market-led Theory of Change.
48 HOPE was led by the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics
49 (ICRISAT), an IARC with the global mandate for research on sorghum and millets, ⁱ commonly
50 known as 'dryland cereals' after the environment in which they are grown. ⁱⁱ In Eastern Africa,
51 HOPE Phase I (2009-2013) targeted four countries – Ethiopia, Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania.
52 In the project areas, the adoption of improved varieties was expected to reach 50 % of the
53 area planted to sorghum and finger millet, while average yields were expected to increase by
54 35 – 40 % (BMGF, 2009). The incentive to raise productivity would come from market
55 opportunities that increased cash income from the sale of dryland cereals.

56 In this paper, we explore the rationale for this Theory of Change and its relevance for Eastern
57 Africa. We argue that, while market-led development was a response to market liberalization,
58 ICRISAT also saw it as a way to replicate the Green Revolution in an environment that was
59 unfavourable for cereal production. HOPE found evidence to vindicate this Theory, but only in
60 part. Despite examples of successful commercialisation, this did not necessarily lead to higher
61 productivity even when farmers adopted improved varieties. Dryland cereals were usually
62 unfertilised and planted on marginal land where they gave assured yields in drought years.
63 Any Green Revolution in dryland cereals will therefore be driven primarily by improved
64 varieties that can avoid drought by maturing early. Although a new phase of the project has
65 started to adapt HOPE's original Theory of Change, we conclude that further changes are
66 needed to increase its relevance for Eastern Africa.

67 The general objective of this paper is to explore a market-led Theory of Change for dryland
68 cereals in Eastern Africa. Specifically, we address three research questions:

- 69 1. What arguments did HOPE use to justify this Theory of Change?
- 70 2. How and why did ICRISAT adopt a market-led Theory of Change?
- 71 3. Does the evidence from HOPE suggest the need for a revised Theory of Change?

72 The paper is organised as follows. The next section offers a close reading of the rhetoric of
73 HOPE's Theory of Change. Section three traces the evolution of market discourse within
74 ICRISAT and asks why it became so influential. Section four uses the evidence generated by
75 the HOPE project to explore the relevance of a market-led Theory of Change for dryland
76 cereals in Eastern Africa. The final section concludes.

77 **2. Theory of Change as Rhetoric**

78 Rhetoric is the art of persuasion. A project proposal is an exercise in persuasion where the
79 rhetoric of economics is on full display. Leading the charge in this rhetorical offensive is the
80 project's Theory of Change. A Theory of Change is formally defined as 'a causal chain of
81 inputs, processes and outcomes that lead to impact' (Douthewaite and Hoffecker, 2017: 89).
82 Yet they are also stories, with a structure, a plot, and the bonus of a happy ending (McCloskey,
83 1998). HOPE's story went like this:

84 *'Dryland areas in West/Central Africa (WCA) and East/Southern Africa (ESA) are*
85 *among the poorest and most food-insecure areas on earth...Most of the inhabitants of*
86 *these areas struggle to wrest a meager living from agriculture using subsistence*

87 cultivation methods. Tragically, they are missing out on large potential productivity
88 gains that are biologically possible given the soils, crops and climates of these areas,
89 as proven by decades of research across a wide range of dryland locations. Yields
90 could potentially be doubled or tripled from their current low levels...On a percentage
91 basis, these gains are as large as those achieved in the famous Green Revolution for
92 rice and wheat. Capturing even a modest portion of these potential gains would
93 generate major impacts in reducing food insecurity and increasing incomes in these
94 impoverished areas.

95 Why, then has this not already happened? One reason has been the dominance in
96 development thinking of the “Green Revolution model” itself. This model of intensive
97 high-yield agriculture was very successful where it was possible to minimize natural
98 resource constraints, e.g. through irrigation and large applications of fertilizers,
99 providing homogeneous, low-stress, high-yielding growing conditions for crops...

100 However, this approach has been less successful for crops and farming systems in
101 rainfed dryland environments where irrigation is impractical and natural resource
102 constraints are more difficult to alleviate. Governments have been reluctant to invest
103 in such areas, even though evidence indicates high returns on investments...Given
104 the stresses and variability of the rainfed drylands, a different approach is needed —
105 one that adapts to environmental variability and risks, rather than assuming that
106 homogenization will occur. Integrated approaches are needed that create synergies
107 between natural resource management and crop breeding...

108 Increasing grain production, though, is not enough. Experience shows that bumper
109 yields of dryland crops soon create a glut on the market, because market outlets for
110 these crops have stagnated or declined, largely due to policy biases against them. This
111 phenomenon traces to the impacts of the Green Revolution across the developing
112 world that favored three crops that require too much moisture to be grown the drylands:
113 rice, wheat and corn. As these crops were heavily promoted and subsidized heavily in
114 urban areas, they replaced traditional demand for the dryland crops.

115 As a result of these two dynamics - lack of adaptive approaches to raise productivity
116 combined with shrinking markets - dryland farmers found themselves unable to profit
117 by investing in commercial production. Instead, they coped by only cultivating these
118 crops at a subsistence level, seeking only to feed their families. A vicious cycle then
119 fed on itself: with less production and less market demand, there was less justification
120 for investment in dryland crops and for the research, development, support services
121 and infrastructure needed to commercialize them, resulting in even further declines in
122 market demand....

123 Overcoming dryland Africa’s stagnant food production trend requires the growth,
124 expansion and diversification of markets for dryland crops, so that farmers will be
125 rewarded for increasing their production and productivity. In recent years, major new
126 trends towards increasing demand for dryland cereals have begun to emerge that
127 provide a renewed opportunity for sorghum and millets in the marketplace. These are
128 long-term trends based on fundamental increases in the driving factors that underlie
129 demand, as described below. **The main thrust of this Project is to provide poor
130 dryland households with the technologies, linkages, and development impetus
131 they need to harness the “pull” of these growing markets’.** (BMGF, 2009, pp. 4-6,
132 emphasis in original)

133 A close reading of HOPE's Theory of Change reveals rich examples of rhetoric. First, there is
134 the way the problem was framed, or 'what and whom are included or excluded' (Gasper and
135 Apthorpe, 1996: 8). Institutions define problems by what they can do to solve them. As an
136 agricultural research centre with expertise in biophysical sciences and in economics, ICRISAT
137 framed the problem of 'the drylands' as one of 'the environment' and of 'markets'. This does
138 not mean that ICRISAT's framing was wrong or irrelevant, but that it reflected its capabilities.
139 A similar process of 'framing' the problem to fit the institutional context has been observed in
140 other agriculture for development projects (Ferguson, 1994).

141 HOPE's Theory of Change took a 'physicalist' approach to agricultural development. A
142 physicalist approach 'focuses on agriculture as a pattern of physical production rooted in
143 circumstances of land and water scarcity' (Apthorpe, 1984: 129). ICRISAT's characterisation
144 of the environment as 'the drylands' epitomises this approach. On the other hand, HOPE's
145 Theory of Change did not view poverty in the drylands as caused solely by biophysical factors,
146 but also by economic factors like the absence of markets. However, the Theory viewed
147 markets not as human institutions but in physicalist terms as a 'dynamic' that will 'pull' or 'drive'
148 investment. Changes to markets were viewed mechanistically in terms of market 'trends',
149 'forces', and 'linkages' (Apthorpe, 1996).

150 A physicalist approach sees the problem as the solution. 'In physicalist discourse, land-water
151 is both the master-key *and* the chief obstacle to rural development' (Apthorpe, 1984: 130).
152 Thus, the problem of the environment can be overcome by adapting new technology. Similarly,
153 HOPE's Theory of Change saw the solution to the problem of old, shrinking markets as new,
154 growing markets, which were assumed to be 'profitable' and 'rewarding'. This neatly side-
155 stepped the political issue of 'policy biases' in these older markets. Despite these similarities,
156 however, there was also a contrast between the treatment of the environment and of markets.
157 While the discussion of the environment focused on what it made the drylands different, the
158 discussion of markets saw them as a universal solution that will work in all environments and
159 for all types of farmer.

160 A striking feature of HOPE's Theory of Change is the absence of human agency. Biophysical
161 forces and markets were 'dynamic', but farmers were not. Technology 'adapts' but not farmers.
162 Obscuring the agency of farmers is achieved in two ways. One is through nominalisation or
163 changing verbs into nouns. 'Growing, expanding, diversifying' which are human activities
164 become 'the growth, expansion, and diversification of markets'. This changes a process over
165 which farmers might be expected to have some control into a fact, or even a natural force, in
166 which it is impossible to intervene ('a vicious cycle'). The second way is by using the passive
167 voice. Farmers 'find themselves' unable to profit (not 'cannot' profit), or farmers will 'be
168 rewarded' by markets (not reward themselves). The only agency allowed in this narrative is
169 for governments, which are portrayed as the villains of the piece ('policy biases') and for the
170 HOPE project, which 'will provide' farmers with 'what they need' (farmers do not 'demand').
171 Rhetoric is used to inflate the role of the HOPE project and relegate farmers to a secondary
172 role.

173 Finally, rhetoric is used to make the 'drylands' a deserving candidate for agricultural research.
174 One is by using the metaphor of the Green Revolution. HOPE's Theory of Change uses the
175 Green Revolution as a foil to emphasise the challenge posed by a different environment ('this
176 model of intensive high-yield agriculture was very successful where it was possible to minimize
177 natural resource constraints'). By characterising the drylands as un-privileged, HOPE
178 'exposes the politics' of focusing research and development only on favourable environments.
179 A second way is by using opposite words. The narrative is saturated with them. They include
180 irrigated/rainfed, low-stress/risky, homogenous/variable, shrinking/growing,

181 subsistence/commercial. Because the first word is always the privileged one, these are called
182 'verbal hierarchies' (McCloskey, 1998). However, the problem of the drylands may be more
183 complex than can be expressed in these simple dichotomies. Opposites leave no room for
184 ambiguity.

185 Using evidence from a grant proposal to deconstruct HOPE's Theory of Change is open to
186 several objections. Grant proposals may be seen as a soft target because they are a 'sales
187 pitch' that should not be judged by 'scientific' standards. On the other hand, all research
188 outputs (including journal articles) are exercises in persuasion (McCloskey, 1988). The
189 difference is one of degree rather than kind. And why should research outputs by the IARCs
190 be judged solely by conventional scientific criteria? Grant proposals are not addressed to an
191 academic audience, but this should not place them beyond critical scrutiny. Scientists devote
192 much time and thought to these documents. They can give valuable insights into strategic
193 thinking and reveal (sometimes unconsciously) basic assumptions which may rarely be
194 articulated and remain hidden to those outside the organisation. A second objection is that
195 grant proposals are tailored to a donor's priorities and parts of a project will be emphasized in
196 order to make their alignment with a specific donor's preferred area of investment clear.
197 Admittedly, the authors of HOPE's Theory of Change were not upon oath. Yet some of the
198 same ideas and even some of the same words can be found in earlier ICRISAT documents.ⁱⁱⁱ
199 This suggests that HOPE's Theory of Change captured important elements of mainstream
200 thinking within ICRISAT. A final objection is that the views expressed in HOPE's Theory of
201 Change do not represent the views of all ICRISAT scientists. However, IARCs are not
202 monolithic organisations but contain a diversity of views. We should not expect HOPE's
203 Theory of Change to command universal agreement. Other scientists would contest its view
204 of farmer agency, for example. After all, ICRISAT has a long and distinguished record of
205 farmer participation in plant breeding. Thus, there may be a gap between the project's Theory
206 of Change and its actual practice. Nevertheless, it seems reasonable to conclude that HOPE's
207 Theory of Change reflects the views of some influential ICRISAT scientists as well as decision-
208 makers in the BMGF.

209 **3. Theory of Change as Discourse**

210 In 2000 ICRISAT's research strategy for dryland cereals was focused on supply. The aim was
211 to raise productivity through 'Integrated Genetic Natural Resource Management' (IGNRM) or
212 a combination of improved varieties and crop management (Twomlow et. al., 2008). In
213 contrast, by 2010 ICRISAT's research strategy was focused on demand, and the aim was to
214 drive growth in productivity by improving access to markets. What explains this change in
215 strategy? First and foremost, ICRISAT's market-led strategy was a response to the
216 opportunities for commercialisation created by market liberalisation. Obviously, this strategy
217 has much to recommend it. Our aim is not to deny the value of this approach. Rather, the aim
218 is to understand the process which led to it being applied to dryland cereals and why it became
219 a universal model.

220 *How did market discourse evolve?*

221 Within ICRISAT, a key driver of market discourse was the experience of the Sorghum and
222 Millet Improvement Programme (SMIP). Remarkably, this project lasted 20 years (1983-2003).
223 A retrospective by the project economist documented the programme's creeping conversion
224 to market-led development (Rohrbach et. al., 2004). SMIP was conceived as a response to
225 drought in southern Africa.^{iv} Initially, the problem was framed as low and variable crop yields,
226 to which the solution was higher and more stable yields. The breeders set to work. Within 10
227 years, 20 improved varieties had been released. Yet although several of these varieties were
228 widely adopted, the impact on yields was disappointing. Without a market for the crop, farmers

229 refused to invest in improved crop management. SMIP redefined the problem of low
230 productivity as 'lack of market demand'. A food technologist was hired to develop a range of
231 new products that would create this demand, only to discover that most of these products
232 could be made more cheaply using maize. As the programme's economist explained:

233 *'This left a conundrum. Commercial grain processors showed little interest in sorghum and*
234 *pearl millet because they were not readily available at prices competitive with maize. On the*
235 *other hand, farmers refused to expand production because commercial demand was limited'*.
236 (Rohrbach *et. al.*, 2004: 83).

237 Yet again, the problem of low productivity was re-defined, this time as 'lack of market linkages'.
238 The solution was direct contracting to reduce transaction costs and ensure that buyers had a
239 consistent supply. What had begun as a research programme to generate scientific knowledge
240 ended up as a development programme focused on utilisation and markets (Hall, 2006).

241 SMIP's experience became the template for a project design which integrated improved
242 varieties, crop management and access to markets (Alumira and Heinrich, 2003). ICRISAT's
243 *Vision and Strategy to 2015* called for technology that met 'the needs of market-oriented and
244 commercializing farmers as well as subsistence-oriented and chronically poor rural
245 households... (ICRISAT, 2006: 43-45). Market discourse culminated in ICRISAT's new
246 Strategic Plan, which unveiled a unifying framework called Inclusive Market-Oriented
247 Development (IMOD) (ICRISAT, 2010a). IMOD was a stage-theory of agricultural
248 development in which resource-poor farmers graduated from subsistence to commercial
249 agriculture. The 'engine of growth' powering this process was the re-investment in agriculture
250 of the income from crop sales, which set in motion a virtuous cycle of growth. The 'springboard'
251 that launched this cycle was higher productivity from dryland cereals. IMOD mainstreamed
252 market discourse within ICRISAT, extending market-led development to cover both India and
253 SSA:

254 *'One of the greatest strengths of the unifying framework of IMOD is its universality. In all*
255 *regions of the globe, connections to markets are the most effective means for escaping*
256 *poverty'* (ICRISAT, 2010a: 23).

257 **Figure 1. Inclusive Market-Oriented Development (IMOD)**

259 Source: ICRISAT (2010a).

260 Evidence to support this strategy for dryland cereal was available. There was the odyssey of
 261 SMIP in Southern Africa, for instance, and the success of pearl millet in India, where adoption
 262 of hybrid varieties was driven by the market for poultry feed (Kumara Charyulu *et. al.*, 2014).
 263 But there was also contrary evidence, of which we give two examples. Significantly, both
 264 examples are based on research approaches that put farmer agency at the heart of their
 265 analysis.

266 The first example is from Farming Systems Research (FSR). Farmers in Burkina Faso growing
 267 pearl millet did not want improved varieties that gave higher yields. Instead, they wanted
 268 varieties that gave low but assured yields on poor soils, and which allowed them to extend
 269 cultivation to marginal land. Fertiliser was applied only to crops planted on soils with higher
 270 production potential that gave higher returns. This pattern was found not only in West Africa.
 271 A similar story emerged from FSR in Sudan.^v Likewise, in Kenya and Zimbabwe, while maize
 272 was planted on heavier, more fertile soils that gave higher yields in wetter years, dryland
 273 cereals were planted on lighter, less fertile soils that gave higher yields in drier years (Chuma
 274 *et. al.*, 2001; Crowley and Carter, 2000). From the perspective of FSR, therefore, the focus on
 275 higher productivity misunderstood the role of dryland cereals in the farming system. As
 276 ICRISAT's FSR economist concluded:

277 *'This is the paradox facing millet improvement programs...It is clear that major improvements*
 278 *in millet yields can only occur through higher input management systems. However, it is not*
 279 *clear that breeding for quantum yield increases within high input systems is a relevant or even*
 280 *realistic objective... [breeders] should consider low input management on marginal land types*
 281 *as the most probable adoption in the foreseeable future'* (Matlon, 1987: 244).^{vi}

282 The second example comes from the Sustainable Livelihoods Approach (SLA). In southern
 283 Africa, SMIP justified its objective of raising productivity on the grounds that food-deficit
 284 households lacked the cash income they needed to buy food (House and Rohrbach, 1991).

285 However, the SLA showed that farmers in Zimbabwe found it more profitable to improve
286 household food security not by raising the yield of sorghum and millets but by investing in
287 livestock which they could sell to buy maize. In preferring this option, ICRISAT's economists
288 conceded, farmers were 'probably correct' (Rohrbach and Alumira, 2002: 22). The SLA
289 therefore sent a clear message: smallholders already had a strategy for household food
290 security, and it involved not only crops but livestock.

291 Equally if not more important in the evolution of market discourse were the external influences.
292 One was the CGIAR. To align itself with the Millennium Development Goals, the CGIAR had
293 revised its strategic objectives to include poverty reduction. To meet this objective, ICRISAT
294 was required to develop a new strategy (CGIAR Science Council, 2008). A background report
295 recommended the World Bank's typology of 'three worlds of agriculture' – from 'agriculture-
296 based' to 'transforming', and finally 'urbanised' agriculture – as a suitable model for this
297 strategy (Walker, 2010). According to ICRISAT's Director General, this typology 'resonated
298 with our own experiences... we chose to incorporate the Bank's lessons, along with our own
299 learning of more than three decades and those of our partners, into our strategic planning
300 process... and thus was born our new strategy...' (Dar and Tiwari, 2012: 93; Dar and Tiwari,
301 2014: 94). ICRISAT used the typology to conceptualise IMOD as a 'a development pathway...
302 from impoverished subsistence farming to prosperous market-oriented farming' (Dar and
303 Tiwari, 2014: 95). The new strategy therefore combined the objectives of poverty reduction
304 and higher productivity: markets would simultaneously give farmers the incentive to raise
305 productivity and generate the cash income needed to reduce poverty. IMOD was ICRISAT's
306 answer to the CGIAR's demand for a strategic Theory of Change focused on poverty reduction
307 (ICRISAT, nd.).

308 A second external influence was the BMGF. With the advent of 'philanthro-capitalism', the
309 Foundation became ICRISAT's biggest single donor, supplying 18 % of its grant income
310 (ICRISAT, 2010b). But the BMGF's influence went beyond funding. Its agricultural programme
311 was led by management consultants who saw smallholder agriculture through commercial
312 eyes. Its projects, with their 'value propositions' and 'product lines', spoke the language of
313 business. Since 'few of these individuals possessed first-hand knowledge of smallholder
314 agriculture', they relied on a universal model of agriculture for development that emphasised
315 scale and replicability (Schurman, 2018: 183).^{vii} The result was mega-projects with quantitative
316 targets used to measure results, and close monitoring to ensure compliance.^{viii} This was
317 reflected in the design of the HOPE project, with its budget of USD 21 million covering 11
318 countries.

319 *Why was market discourse so influential?*

320 Market discourse was championed by ICRISAT's Director General, who identified himself with
321 IMOD – 'As a transformational leader, I introduced the approach called Inclusive Market
322 Oriented Development' (ICRISAT, 2014b) – hailing it as 'original' and 'historic' (Dar and Tiwari,
323 2014: 93). Appointed to an unprecedented third term in 2009, his authority had never been
324 greater. The new strategy was swiftly institutionalised. IMOD was made the theme of
325 ICRISAT's bi-annual Global Planning Meeting in 2013, attended by all internationally -
326 recruited staff. Rival teams of researchers competed on how best to promote the new strategy
327 (the winning team composed an IMOD song). Three specialists were hired to 'implement'
328 IMOD. Two volumes of Kuhnian 'exemplars' were commissioned, re-casting past research
329 projects into the IMOD framework (ICRISAT, 2014, 2015). Market discourse became the new
330 orthodoxy.

331 But the decisive reason why market discourse became so influential was the spell cast by the
332 Green Revolution. ICRISAT's *raison d'être* was that the Green Revolution had 'bypassed' the

333 semi-arid tropics. The remedy was a ‘Grey to Green Revolution’ for the drylands (ICRISAT,
334 2001).^{ix} India’s original Green Revolution was led by the International Maize and Wheat
335 Improvement Centre (CIMMYT) and International Rice Research Institute (IRRI). IRRI’s
336 research priority – defined for it by the Rockefeller Foundation – was to raise yield per unit of
337 land. Productivity was viewed as an ‘isolable’ technical problem, meaning that it could be
338 isolated from its spatial, socio-economic and political context and treated as universal:

339 *‘IRRI’s planners were interested in isolates, not patterns; in variables, not systems; in*
340 *universality not locality’* (Anderson et. al., 1991: 52).

341 Today this focus on productivity seems self-evident, but it was not so at the time.^x The success
342 of the Green Revolution in rice set the pattern for ICRISAT, which followed IRRI’s lead.^{xi} Yet
343 adopting higher productivity as ICRISAT’s research priority for dryland cereals posed a
344 strategic dilemma. In an unfavourable production environment, farmers lacked the economic
345 incentive to invest in raising productivity. It was this dilemma that produced the ‘paradoxes’
346 and ‘conundrums’ which gave ICRISAT’s economists sleepless nights. Finally, however, they
347 hit on a solution – link farmers with markets. The priority given to raising productivity helps
348 explain why market discourse became so influential. ICRISAT saw market-led development
349 as its only hope of replicating a Green Revolution of the kind witnessed in Asia.

350 **4. Changing the Theory of Change**

351 *‘It should be mandatory for all projects that by the end they should have changed their*
352 *Theory of Change’.* Robert Chambers^{xii}

353 A rhetorical analysis of development discourse is not concerned with whether Theories of
354 Change are true or false. Rather, they ‘give the economist a place to look in from outside’
355 (McCloskey, 2001: 20) or help ‘to train ourselves to see what culturally we have been taught
356 to overlook’ (Escobar, 2012: 113). In this section, the focus shifts to the empirical basis for
357 HOPE’s Theory of Change. The HOPE project successfully increased the supply of new
358 varieties of sorghum and millets and smallholders’ access to quality seed of improved varieties
359 (BMGF, 2015). But it had less impact on the demand side, or in linking smallholders with new
360 markets and stimulating commercialisation. A recent synthesis of the evidence from HOPE’s
361 socio-economic research has analysed the reasons for this lack of impact (Orr et. al., 2020).
362 In this section, we relate this research evidence to HOPE’s Theory of Change. How far does
363 the evidence support this Theory and, if not, how can the Theory be made more appropriate
364 for dryland cereals in Eastern Africa?

365 *Evidence*

366 The ideal way to test a Theory of Change is through an impact evaluation that compares
367 changes over the life of the project for matched treatment and control groups. Unfortunately,
368 in the case of HOPE, such an evaluation was made only for Tanzania (Orr and Muange, 2015)
369 but not for Kenya, Uganda or Ethiopia. What follows, therefore, is not an impact evaluation of
370 the HOPE project. Instead, the aim is use evidence from HOPE to review some of its
371 assumptions about commercialisation. Table 1 collates evidence from five household surveys
372 conducted by HOPE. Since the surveys were not representative at the national level, and there
373 are gaps, the evidence is suggestive rather than conclusive.

374 HOPE found evidence that dryland cereals could be successfully commercialised (Table 1).
375 One example is the value chain for clear sorghum beer in Kenya where, within six years,
376 Senator keg became Kenya’s best-selling beer (Orr et. al., 2013). Another is the value chain
377 for finger millet, used to produce a nutritious flour often used as weaning food (Schipmann-
378 Schwarze et. al., 2015). In Tanzania, Uganda, and Kenya between 45 and 81 % of finger millet

379 was sold. Commercialisation was profitable, ranging from 56 USD ha⁻¹ for sorghum in Kenya
380 to over 140 USD ha⁻¹ for finger millet in Kenya and Tanzania. Commercialisation was socially
381 inclusive, and not restricted to larger, 'commercial' farmers. In Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda,
382 the two smallest farm quartiles also sold sorghum and finger millet. Thus, HOPE provided
383 textbook examples of smallholder commercialisation, supplying value chains that were
384 expanding rapidly, fuelled by urbanisation, rising aspirations and a growing middle class with
385 the income to spend on processed food.

386 However, the scale of commercialisation was limited. For the four countries, commercial
387 demand from three value chains – beer, flour, and feed – accounted for just 6 % of the total
388 current production of sorghum and 11% of millets (Orr et. al., 2017). Projecting market demand
389 to 2025 under favourable assumptions increased demand to 12 % of total supply for millets
390 and 15 % for sorghum (Orr et. al., 2017). Moreover, the number of smallholders supplying
391 these markets was small – just 13,000 smallholders in the region were contracted directly in
392 the value chain for sorghum beer (Orr et. al., 2017). Consequently, the primary demand for
393 dryland cereals continued to be home consumption. For the foreseeable future, therefore, the
394 main incentive for intensification will not be commercialisation but the need to improve
395 household food security.

396

397

398 **Table 1. Commercialisation of sorghum and millets in HOPE project areas, Eastern Africa**

Crop	Kenya		Tanzania		Uganda	Ethiopia	
	Sorghum	Finger Millet	Sorghum	Finger Millet	Finger Millet	Sorghum	Finger Millet
Project area (district)	Kitui	Teso, Busia, Butere-Mumias	Kondoa, Singida Rural	Kondoa, Singida Rural	Lila, Kole, Serere	Mieso, Kobo	Shalla
Year of survey	2012	2012	2010	2010	2015	2011	2011
Sample households (no.)	300	270	360	360	190	260	130
Share of crop sold (%)	100	45	14	81	60	34	14
Average quantity sold (kg), by farm size quartile:							
I (smallest)	235	Na.	11	199	104	Na.	Na.
II	312		33	183	100		
III	516		50	234	105		
IV	697		82	346	201		
Gross margin (USD ha ⁻¹) ^a	56 ^b	143 ^c	0 ^d	74 ^d	146 ^e	Na.	Na.
Adoption of improved varieties (% farmers)	73	49	61	0	31	38	37
Applied inorganic fertiliser? (Yes/No)	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes

399 Sources:

400 Kenya: Orr et al., (2013), Handschuch (2014). Tanzania: Schipmann et. al., (2014); Uganda: Mwema et. al., (2017); Ethiopia (Bekele et al., 2012).

401 Notes:

402 ^a cash-cost basis (excluding cost of family labour).403 ^{bc} Exchange rate: 1 USD = 85 Kenyan shillings.404 ^d Exchange rate: 1 USD = 1,215 Tanzanian shillings.405 ^e Exchange rate: 1 USD = 2,600 Ugandan shillings.

406 Finally, the evidence for market-led intensification was mixed. Improved varieties were often
407 widely adopted, where they existed and where farmers had access to seed. These included a
408 low-tannin sorghum suitable for clear sorghum beer in Kenya, and improved varieties of finger
409 millet in Kenya and Uganda (Table 1). However, commercialisation did not always increase
410 growers' investment in cash inputs. Except for finger millet in Kenya and Ethiopia, none of
411 these crops received inorganic fertiliser, including the two crops with the highest levels of
412 commercialisation – sorghum in Kenya and finger millet in Tanzania (Table 1). As a result,
413 improved varieties did not always result in higher yields. Improved varieties of finger millet in
414 Uganda gave higher yields than local varieties even without fertiliser (Mwema et. al., 2017).
415 But in Tanzania, no significant difference was found between the yields of improved and local
416 varieties of sorghum (Schipmann et. al., 2014). A re-survey of the same households four years
417 later confirmed this result (Orr and Muange, 2015).^{xiii}

418 In sum, the evidence partially vindicates HOPE's Theory of Change. Dryland cereals can be
419 commercialised in ways that benefit poorer smallholders. However, the success of these value
420 chains should not mask the facts that commercialisation has had limited effects on
421 productivity, and that they remain islands of commercialisation in a sea of subsistence
422 agriculture.

423 *Adaptation*

424 Partly as a result of learning in Phase I, Phase II of the HOPE project (2017-2021) dropped its
425 focus on commercialisation to focus on increasing the adoption of improved varieties by
426 increasing farmers' access to quality seed (BMGF, 2015). However, this change was not the
427 result of second thoughts about the relevance of market-led growth but an admission that
428 increasing the commercial demand for dryland cereals was beyond the project's control.
429 Arguably, adaptation needs to go further and address some of the issues raised in this paper.

430 One puzzle of a market-led Theory of Change for dryland cereals is why farmers have adopted
431 improved varieties despite the absence of markets. The obvious answer is higher yields. As
432 we have seen, however, this was not always the case. Indeed, the history of improved varieties
433 of dryland cereals in SSA is one of adoption *without* higher yields (Ahmed et. al., 2000). At the
434 start of the project, in three of HOPE's four target countries in Eastern Africa there had been
435 no increase in the yield of dryland cereals for 20 years – the exception being Ethiopia (Orr et.
436 al., 2016). One reason for this, as we have seen, is that farmers did not always apply inorganic
437 fertiliser. This was not because it was unprofitable. HOPE showed that micro-dosing sorghum
438 with 30 kg ha⁻¹ was profitable in both Kenya and Ethiopia (Orr et. al., 2020). However, growers
439 may lack access to fertiliser or ration the amount they apply. Farmers may also plant dryland
440 cereals on less fertile land. Given the high cost of inorganic fertiliser, it would be rational to
441 apply this only to land and to crops that gave higher returns. Yet HOPE's ambition to raise
442 average yields of dryland cereals by one-third was predicated on commercial growers
443 investing in inorganic fertiliser.

444 If not higher yields, an alternative incentive for adoption was early maturity. Two-thirds of
445 improved varieties of sorghum and half of the improved varieties of finger millet in Eastern
446 Africa are classed as 'early-maturing' (Orr et. al., 2020). Admittedly, early maturity has some
447 disadvantages.^{xiv} But it also has two advantages. First, early – maturing varieties escape
448 drought: they can be harvested even if the rains start late or finish early, providing an assured
449 yield in all but the worst years. Second, by accelerating the harvest date, early maturing
450 varieties shorten the hungry period, sometimes by as much as two months (Orr et. al., 2020).
451 For food-deficit smallholders in the drought-prone drylands, these are powerful incentives for
452 adoption. Historically, one reason for the rapid spread of maize in Africa was that it matured
453 earlier than sorghum (McCann, 2005). Today, the main reason given by farmers in Tanzania

454 for adopting improved varieties of sorghum is that they are early - maturing (Monyo et. al.,
455 2004).

456 The importance of dryland cereals for food security has implications for HOPE's Theory of
457 Change. First, it limits the potential for commercialisation. In drought years, food-deficit
458 smallholders may prioritise food security and reduce sales in favour of home consumption.
459 For example, when drought struck eastern Kenya in 2011, two thirds of the smallholders who
460 had contracted to sell sorghum to East African Breweries Limited refused to sell even part of
461 their harvest (Esipisu, 2011). Second, commercialisation is still possible for small farms. The
462 evidence on social inclusion suggests that the verbal hierarchy of 'subsistence/commercial'
463 farmers is misleading. In Eastern Africa, where the vast majority farmers are food deficit, these
464 two categories are one and the same. Third, the importance of food security raises questions
465 about the nature of a Green Revolution for dryland cereals. The Green Revolution in Asia
466 showed that the increase in productivity required to lower cereal prices was easier to achieve
467 in favourable production environments (Otsuka and Yamano, 2005). For food-deficit
468 smallholders in the drylands, maize grown in favourable environments that succeeds in
469 reducing food prices may do more to improve household food security than higher productivity
470 from dryland cereals.^{xv} However, this assumes that maize will always be available at an
471 affordable price. An alternative view is that household food security does require higher
472 productivity in dryland cereals, but that this Green Revolution will be of a different kind. The
473 Green Revolution in Asia was a seed-fertiliser revolution, but a Green Revolution for dryland
474 cereals in Eastern Africa may be based on seed without fertiliser. If so, any impact on
475 productivity will be felt chiefly in poor seasons, when early maturity helps avoid crop losses.
476 Yield stability – higher yields in drought years – may prove to be the key to this Green
477 Revolution.

478 Finally, a revised Theory of Change needs to address the issue of universality. This Theory is
479 founded on a linked series of generalisations. The CGIAR generalised the 'high modernism'
480 of scientific agriculture with its goal of higher productivity to all farming systems and
481 environments (Scott, 1998). ICRISAT then generalised a market-led strategy of agriculture for
482 development (IMOD) to its three regions and five mandate crops. Finally, HOPE generalised
483 this market-led strategy into a Theory of Change for dryland cereals for 11 countries and two
484 continents. However, these generalisations ignored differences in context. Stage theory
485 assumes an inevitable progression – the only difference is one of timing – while mega-projects
486 favour scale and replicability over local context. The result was a Theory of Change that under-
487 valued heterogeneity between regions as well as farmer agency – the variety of reasons why
488 farmers grew dryland cereals. A revised Theory of Change should include these as core
489 assumptions.

490 Which brings us back to the metaphor of the hedgehog and the fox. HOPE's market-led Theory
491 of Change and ICRISAT's IMOD are part of a wider shift in research strategy for dryland
492 cereals within the CGIAR. The first CGIAR Research Programme for Dryland Cereals (2012-
493 2017) distinguished two target groups of 'subsistence' and 'commercial' smallholders, with
494 separate 'product-lines' for each group. The CGIAR itself insisted on this distinction.^{xvi} This
495 view of smallholder agriculture harks back to a modernist model of agricultural development
496 in which smallholders graduate from subsistence to commercial agriculture. This model has
497 been criticised by both anthropologists (Hill, 1986) and historians (Thorner, 1971), who argue
498 that what distinguishes economies based on smallholder agriculture is the *coexistence* of
499 subsistence and market elements. Or in the words of a standard textbook, 'The defining
500 feature of a smallholder household is its *partial integration* into markets' (Ellis, 1993: 10,
501 emphasis added). Thus, the verbal hierarchy of 'subsistence/commercial' farmers in HOPE's
502 Theory of Change misses something fundamental about smallholder households, namely that

503 they combine a subsistence and a market orientation within the same household. Smallholders
504 are hybrids, with one foot in the market and the other in the subsistence economy. This 'double
505 orientation' (Thorner, 1971: 207) of smallholder households gives them an ambivalent view of
506 market-led development:

507 *'The relationship of peasants to the market contains a continuous tension between the risky*
508 *advantages of market participation and the conservation of a non-market basis for survival'*
509 *(Ellis, 1993: 6).*

510 This tension between subsistence and market objectives helps explain why it has proved
511 difficult to commercialise dryland cereals in Eastern Africa. It also has implications for a
512 market-led Theory of Change. The double orientation of smallholder agriculture means that it
513 does not fit easily into a universal model that focuses exclusively on market development as
514 the driver for the adoption of new technology and higher productivity. Smallholder agriculture
515 requires a flexible Theory of Change that recognises differences not only in context and
516 between farmers, but also differences in objectives within the same household. In other words,
517 a Theory of Change less like the hedgehog, which knows just one big thing, and more like the
518 fox, which knows many things.

519

520 **5. Conclusion**

521 Theories of Change have become the vogue for agricultural research and development
522 projects. The HOPE project applied a market-led Theory of Change to dryland cereals in
523 Eastern Africa. The 'problem' of dryland agriculture was framed as one of low productivity.
524 The economic incentive to raise productivity required linking farmers with markets. Market-led
525 development would then allow ICRISAT to achieve a Green Revolution in the drylands. This
526 logic culminated in a new research strategy which combined the research objective of raising
527 productivity with the development objective of poverty reduction. ICRISAT's IMOD strategy
528 adopted a stage-theory of agricultural development which assumed that dryland agriculture in
529 Asia and Africa was on the same evolutionary escalator that led from subsistence to
530 commercial agriculture.

531 In Eastern Africa, this Theory gave mixed results. On the one hand, there were cases of
532 successful commercialisation. On the other hand, commercialisation did not automatically
533 result in higher productivity. Farmers adopted improved varieties of dryland cereals but usually
534 grew them without inorganic fertiliser. Moreover, the scale of commercialisation was limited.
535 Sorghum and millets were competitive in the value chains for clear sorghum beer or specialty
536 flour but they were not competitive with maize in the value chains for low-cost staple flours
537 and livestock feed.

538 HOPE has since adapted its Theory of Change to focus on seed supply rather than
539 commercialisation. Arguably, further modifications are required. A revised Theory of Change
540 should give a central role to farmer agency. This requires a better understanding of why
541 farmers grow dryland cereals and why they value improved varieties of these crops. In Eastern
542 Africa, dryland cereals are grown primarily to protect household food security in drought years.
543 This may limit potential gains in productivity, suggesting a different kind of Green Revolution
544 for dryland cereals. Finally, a revised Theory should avoid a universal model but respect
545 differences between regions and farmers' objectives.

546

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ⁱ Millets includes both pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) and finger millet (*Eleusine coracana*). Pearl millet is widely grown in Southern Africa and finger millet in Eastern Africa.

ⁱⁱ The drylands include four environments: hyper-arid, arid, semiarid and dry subhumid. The CRP for Dryland Cereals focuses on the semiarid and dry subhumid environments (ICRISAT & Partners, 2017: 6-7).

ⁱⁱⁱ For example, see ICRISAT (2001:3), *'The key to success has been finding ways to adapt cropping systems to the natural variability of the environment, rather than attempting to homogenize the environment with massive inputs...'*, and ICRISAT (2002: 65), *'Adapting the crop to the environment, through better stress, disease, and pest management can result in higher productivity...This approach also helps position them in the global market'*.

^{iv} SMIP covered nine member countries of the Southern African Development Community (SADC): South Africa, Botswana, Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Tanzania, Zambia, and Zimbabwe.

^v In Darfur, improved varieties of sorghum, which matured early, allowed farmers to extend planting to land that was too risky for local varieties with longer field durations and gave higher yields in bad years (Morton, 1996: 119-120). Similarly, in Zimbabwe, *'food security is sought by expanding the cropped area, and possibly the choice of a new, early-maturing variety, rather than the intensification of crop management'* (Rohrbach and Alumira, 2002: 20).

^{vii} However, the BMGF project officer for HOPE, to whom its managers reported, came from the region and had devoted his career as a plant breeder to sorghum and millets.

^{viii} Monitoring was taken to extreme lengths. Phase 1 of the HOPE Project had 1,072 milestones. As a result, annual project meetings were spent scrutinising progress against milestones at the expense of re-thinking strategy or lesson-learning.

^{ix} *'The challenge before us today is, how to replicate the Green Revolution in less hospitable rural agroecoregions... Another revolution is the need of the hour - we may call it the second Green Revolution...'* ICRISAT (2002: 16).

^x IRRI's first economist recalls: *'At a seminar held a short time after my arrival the IRRI Director, Robert Chandler, responded to a question about research priorities by pounding on the table and announcing: "The purpose of this institute is not to do good science!" After a shocked silence he continued: "The purpose of this institute is to raise rice yields in Asia!" Then after a pause he added: "And raising rice yields in Asia may require that you do good science!'. My initial reaction was disbelief. The objective struck me as extremely audacious. In retrospect, however, the objective that Chandler set before the IRRI staff was responsible for establishing an IRRI culture (ideology? dogma?) that was largely responsible for the successful development of modern high yielding rice varieties'* (Ruttan, 2001: 26).

^{xi} Ralph W. Cummings Jnr., ICRISAT's first Director General (1972-77), was previously the Director General of IRRI (1972). From the beginning, the research priority for dryland cereals was higher productivity: *'ICRISAT's main breeding thrust [for sorghum] is aimed at higher and more consistent yields...Breeding goals are the same with millet'* (Spaven, 1977: 51).

^{xii} Intervention at plenary discussion of *'Understanding Change and Impact'*, Development Studies Association Annual Conference, London, 3rd November 2012.

^{xiii} By contrast, an earlier adoption survey by ICRISAT in found that, averaged across poor and normal seasons, improved varieties of sorghum out-yielded local varieties by 10-38 % under farmers' management. This result may reflect the fact that, because they matured earlier, improved varieties gave a higher yield in poor seasons (Monyo et. al., 2004: 14).

^{xiv} In Ethiopia, early maturing varieties of sorghum are unpopular because they are shorter and so provide less straw for fodder, thatching, and fencing (Orr et. al., 2016: 30). Moreover, early maturity puts a ceiling on the adoption of improved varieties. 'Short-season cultivars offer a good risk-reduction strategy for adverse years, but they are generally only adopted on small areas or when the rains fail, because in most years they are less profitable than intermediate or long-season cultivars (Shapiro and Sanders, 2002: 267). If so, the rate of adoption for early-maturing varieties of dryland cereals is unlikely to reach the levels achieved for hybrid maize.

^{xv} Ironically, ICRISAT's former FSR economist in West Africa has now reached the same conclusion: 'Programs to raise productivity should focus on high potential areas...Programs for lower potential food deficit zones should focus instead on stabilizing production, building market links to surplus producing areas...' (Matlon, 2012: 120).

^{xvi} This Program was approved only after two revisions responding to the 'must-haves' required by the Independent Science & Partnership Council (ISPC), which saw new, non-food markets as benefitting 'commercial' farmers, while 'subsistence' farmers benefitted from improved food security (ISPC, 2012a: 2). In response, ICRISAT developed a typology showing a continuum between subsistence and commercial farmers with illustrative impact pathways for each category. This also failed to satisfy the ISPC, which requested a 'better definition of the targeted farmer groups ranging from subsistence farmers to those able to link with commercial markets' (ISPC, 2012b: 1).